

GAIA accuracy: Scaling considerations

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ABSTRACT. Basic constraints and scaling properties for the GAIA astrometric instrument are summarized, assuming that the CCD parameters are fixed. The note is based on a presentation at the 2nd GST meeting (17–18 January 2002).

1 Introduction

The basic parameters determining the final astrometric accuracy of GAIA are (1) the angular size of the diffraction image, (2) the number of detected photons that can be used for centroiding, and (3) the geometric and temporal factors that allow the astrometric parameters to be disentangled. Of course, many other things enter any detailed accuracy analysis (image sampling, readout noise, aberrations, structural stability, and so on), but these are second-order effects as long as certain basic requirements are satisfied. Some of these requirements are rather obvious, e.g. that the aberrations should be small enough that the telescope is essentially diffraction-limited, or that the readout noise should be small compared with the photon noise for typical sources.

In this note I discuss two constraints that are perhaps less obvious, but nevertheless important when different design alternatives for a revised GAIA mission are considered. I then derive the first-order scaling formulas for the astrometric accuracy.

2 Constraints

Among the many requirements for a well-functioning scanning astrometric instrument, we shall here discuss the following two constraints:

- The diffraction image must be sufficiently sampled.
- Successive great-circle scans must overlap in the transverse-field direction.

2.1 Image sampling

The monochromatic diffraction image is an example of a band-limited signal: the highest spatial frequency present is $s_{\max} = D/\lambda$, where D is the linear pupil size and λ the wavelength. The spatial frequency s is expressed in periods per radian. According to

Shannon’s theorem, such a signal can be completely reconstructed (in the noise-less case) from an infinite series of equidistant sample points, provided that their separation is at most $1/2s_{\max}$. When applied to CCD detection of diffraction images, this suggests that the pixel size (in radians) should not exceed $\lambda/2D$. If F is the effective focal length, then the linear pixel size p should satisfy

$$p \leq \frac{F\lambda}{2D}. \quad (1)$$

For astrometry, it is mainly the along-scan direction that matters, so D and p must be the along-scan dimensions of the pupil and pixel.

For GAIA we have carefully studied the centroiding accuracy as function of pixel size and other parameters, and empirically found that a pixel size of $9 \mu\text{m}$ is close to the maximum acceptable for the baseline optical configuration (with $D = 1.7 \text{ m}$, $F = 50 \text{ m}$). This agrees very well with Eq. (1) if we assume an effective wavelength $\lambda = 620 \text{ nm}$, which leads to the condition $p \leq 9.1 \mu\text{m}$.

Having a larger pixel size than this limit makes it very difficult to reach anywhere near the theoretical accuracy (as derived e.g. from the Cramér–Rao bound) by any practical centroiding algorithm. In addition, it seems to make the centroiding inordinately sensitive to calibration errors.

It is therefore very strongly recommended that condition (1) is satisfied for any scaled version of the Astro telescope, with $\lambda = 620 \text{ nm}$ if the QE curve remains roughly the same as in the current baseline (Concept and Technology Study Report). In practice it means that the F/D ratio is retained, or at least not reduced.

2.2 Scan overlap

As explained in SAG–LL–014, the revolving scanning law is probably as close to optimal as we can get with a fixed sun/spin axis angle (ξ). This implies a nearly constant precession rate $|\dot{\mathbf{z}}| \simeq 4.2 \text{ deg day}^{-1} = 175 \text{ mas s}^{-1}$, which is also the maximum transverse scan rate. Actually the precession rate depends weakly on the angle ξ , as described in Table 2 and Eq. (13) of SAG–LL–014. For the interval of interest, $45^\circ \leq \xi \leq 55^\circ$, this can be described to sufficient accuracy by $|\dot{\mathbf{z}}|_{\max} = 5.12 - 0.02\xi \text{ deg day}^{-1}$, where ξ is in degrees.

The scan rate ω (or spin period $P = 2\pi/\omega$) should be such that there is no gap between successive scans. A gap would mean that an object at that position would miss one of the six ‘guaranteed’ observation epochs per year (see Sect. 3 in SAG–LL–014), which in turn would be unfavourable for disentangling the astrometric parameters and, even more, for the determination of additional (orbital) parameters or photometric variability. (Further study should be made to see how serious this really is.)

With ϕ denoting the angular size of the transverse field, the no-gap condition becomes $P|\dot{\mathbf{z}}|_{\max} \leq \phi$, or

$$\omega \geq \frac{76.8 - 0.3\xi}{\phi} \quad (2)$$

where ω is in arcsec s^{-1} and ξ, ϕ are in degrees. For the current baseline ($\xi = 55^\circ$, $\phi = 0.66^\circ$) the scan rate should be at least 91 arcsec s^{-1} , which is amply satisfied by the current $\omega = 120$ arcsec s^{-1} .

Although the scan overlap condition may not be as serious as the sampling condition, I strongly recommend that Eq. (2) is satisfied. In practice it could mean that the scan rate is set by the achievable transverse field.

3 Parallax accuracy versus basic parameters

The basic parameters to consider are:

- D, H = dimensions along and normal to the scan of the Astro pupil;
- d, h = linear dimensions of the Astro focal plane along and normal to the scan;
- F = effective focal length of the Astro instrument;
- L = effective mission length (i.e. excluding dead time);
- ξ = sun/spin axis angle.

We assume that detector properties (QE curve, pixel size, etc) are essentially fixed as in the Study Report. Moreover, we assume that there are always two Astro pupils, so that the total pupil area is $2DH$.

The fundamental formulae for the parallax accuracy are Eq. (13) and (67) in the Study Report (pp. 127 and 262), which we here write as

$$\sigma_\pi \propto \frac{\lambda}{D\sqrt{N} \sin \xi}, \quad (3)$$

where N is the total number of photons detected for a particular star throughout the mission. For a given object, the latter number is of course proportional to the total observing time on the object, τ , and the pupil area:

$$N \propto \tau DH. \quad (4)$$

The mean observing time per object is given by Eq. (14) in the Study Report, from which

$$\tau \propto \Omega L = \frac{dhL}{F^2}, \quad (5)$$

where Ω is the solid angle of the Astro field. Combining Eqs. (3)–(5) we have

$$\sigma_\pi \propto \frac{\lambda F}{D \sin \xi \sqrt{DHdhL}}. \quad (6)$$

If we now assume that the diffraction image is critically sampled, that is we do not use smaller pixels than necessary according to Eq. (1), then $F\lambda/D = 2p$ and

$$\sigma_\pi \propto \frac{p}{\sin \xi \sqrt{DHdhL}}. \quad (7)$$

Thus, for fixed along-scan pixel size p , the parallax accuracy scales inversely proportional to $\sin \xi \sqrt{DHdhL}$.

4 Consequences for a revised mission

In order to reduce cost and simplify the design, it has been suggested to decrease D from 1.7 to 1.5 m, and ξ from 55° to 45° ; partial compensation would be achieved by increasing L from 4 to 5 years. If Hdh remains unchanged, this would lead to an increase in σ_π by 10%. To arrive at the same σ_π , it will be necessary to further increase L and/or the product Hdh by a total 22%.

Other ideas to simplify the design include the use of superposed fields and reducing the spin rate ω . Both of these suggestions have only a second-order effect on the final accuracy, according to the present analysis, provided that the scan overlap condition is respected and the total pupil area is not reduced.